

0D and Quasi 1D modelling of the Rotating Detonation Combustor

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One approach to increase the overall efficiency of a gas turbine cycle is to switch from deflagration combustion to detonation combustion, where combustion happens in the supersonic regime and generates a rise in total pressure of up to 30% during the combustion process. This process is known as Pressure Gain Combustion (PGC). Studies have indicated that PGC can yield a considerable gain in thermal efficiency while also emitting low NO_x levels. In this paper, a reduced order model for Rotating Detonation Combustion is developed, where a quasi 1D approach has been adopted and the flow parameters are calculated and validated with experimental and CFD results. As it is a lower order model, the detonation front is assumed to be straight and the oblique shock strength is assumed to be constant. The detonation wave height is calculated using the fixed ratio of wave height to expansion zone length instead of cell size. The pressure decay model behind the detonation wave is informed by experimental data. The total pressure ratio across the oblique shock is modelled using the shock flow number and entropy generated by the oblique shock. From the results of the quasi 1D model, a 0D approach for the calculation of outlet pressure and temperature is then evaluated. A parametric study for the pressure gain is done with inlet temperature and equivalence ratio. The axial and azimuthal velocity distribution at the inlet and at the outlet are calculated and compared with 2D LES and 3D LES. Overall, the comparison and accuracy of the quasi 1D RDC model with high fidelity simulations and experimental results are reasonable. The motivation of the model is to accurately predict the RDC outlet parameters which can be used for the reduced order cycle analysis.

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Nomenclature

Symbols

A	= area
a	= speed of sound
c_p	= specific heat at constant pressure
C	= circumference of the combustor
f	= frequency
h_{det}	= detonation front height
h	= enthalpy
L	= axial length of combustor
M	= Mach number
\dot{m}	= mass flow rate
P	= pressure
T	= temperature
q	= heat release
R	= gas constant
s	= entropy
sfn	= shock flow number
V	= velocity
w_c	= width of the combustor
Δh_f	= enthalpy of formation
$\Delta\theta_{refilling}$	= refilling zone length
$\Delta\theta_{expansion}$	= expansion zone length
η_c	= combustion efficiency
γ	= specific heat ratio
ϕ	= equivalence ratio
π_{ob}	= pressure ratio of oblique shock
τ	= time period of annulus

Subscripts and Superscripts

$(\cdot)_{an}$	= analytical
$(\cdot)_{avg}$	= average
(\cdot)	= averaged value
$(\cdot)_x$	= axial
$(\cdot)_\theta$	= azimuthal
$(\cdot)_{CJ}$	= chapman–jouguet condition
$(\cdot)_{cr}$	= critical
$(\cdot)_d$	= downstream
$(\cdot)_{inj}$	= injection
$(\cdot)_{ob}$	= oblique shock
$(\cdot)_{out}$	= outlet
$(\cdot)_p$	= plenum
$(\cdot)_z$	= radial
$(\cdot)_u$	= upstream

I. Introduction

The International Air Transportation Association [1] stated that the number of people utilizing air transportation is increasing on an annual basis, which has a variety of benefits but also some drawbacks, such as a rise in emissions from air transportation. For domestic intercity air travel in US [2], the CO_2 emissions averaged 128.4 million tons annually. Estimated CH_4 and NO_x emissions were approximately 5.3 million tons and 1.06 million tons annually.

From a technical point of view, emission reduction from the air transport sector depends on propulsion units. However, the efficiency of aircraft propulsion components, namely gas turbines, has approached its limit during the past decades. The achievement of aviation's long-term emission reduction targets, net zero carbon aviation by 2050, will be difficult to accomplish using conventional technologies. As a result, reconsidering the combustion process is one potential area for achieving a significant increase in propulsion unit efficiency. Pressure Gain Combustors (PGC) can be considered in place of conventional combustors since PGC contributes to a considerable gain in thermal efficiency. PGC is a form of combustion that uses a nonconstant pressure combustion process generate a rise in total pressure up to 30% during the combustion process compared to 2-3% total pressure loss occurring in conventional combustors [3, 4]. Two of the most promising PGC concepts are the Pulse Detonation Combustor (PDC), in which a combustor tube is cyclically filled with fuel-oxidizer mixture and then detonated, and the Rotating Detonation Combustor (RDC), in which the ignition is self-sustained by a rotating detonation wave traveling around the combustor annulus. Several researchers have focused on the integration of PGC into conventional gas turbines, whether in the form of PDC [5, 6], RDC [7, 8], or overall thermodynamic cycle investigations [9].

Several authors have conducted experimental and numerical research to study rotating detonation combustion processes. Among the numerical studies, Schwer et al. [10, 11] designed a 3D RDC and investigated several aspects of hydrogen-air RDC including pressure effects, combustor size and different inlet effects on performance. Sousa et al. [12] modelled RDC using 2D method of characteristics (MOC) followed by a supersonic turbine and studied the overall thermodynamic cycle analysis. On the experimental side, researchers at TU Berlin have investigated different aspects of

RDC experimentally including rotating wave transition [13], reactant mixing characteristics [14], and investigating the effect of outlet restriction on operating mode of the RDC [15].

The order of simulation can be chosen based on the information required from the combustor. For instance, if a detailed analysis of RDC is needed, then 3D CFD can be carried out. For the whole cycle analysis in a low-order model, the outlet parameters of RDC is required, thus a quasi 1D model is sufficient. Studies have shown that reduced order models for RDC can be accurate enough to capture the flow features. Sousa [12] developed a tool for evaluating the time-dependent temperature and pressure at the combustor outlet using method of characteristics, which can be used for the engine analysis and turbine integration. Ji [16] developed a reduced order RDC model and compared it with 3D CFD [10]. The model described in this paper incorporates the model of Ji along with the experimental results from Sichel and Foster [17] and with few modifications such as the calculation of detonation front height is done with the refilling zone length instead of the cell size and the expansion is no longer isentropic. In this work, the inlet and outlet distribution of axial and azimuthal velocities are also calculated and compared with 2D and 3D LES. The pressure distribution at the inlet, pressure gain and total temperature at the outlet are compared with experimental and 3D LES results. The lower order RDC model also investigates the variation of pressure gain with respect to the inlet parameters such as compressor plenum temperature and equivalence ratio. The time period and frequency of the cycle are also determined. From the quasi 1D model, a 0D approach for the calculation of exit pressure and temperature is evaluated.

II. Quasi 1D RDC Model

Fig. 1 RDC Annulus

The numerical simulations from literatures have shown that the main flow features in the RDC can be characterized by one or more detonation waves propagating around the annulus, followed by expansion waves behind the detonation front, an oblique shock and a slip line, as shown in fig. 1a. In this work, as the model is quasi 1D, the detonation front is assumed to be straight and the oblique shock strength is assumed to be constant. From fig. 1a, the pressure behind the detonation wave θ_{det} decays to below the injection pressure at θ_{inj} and the fresh mixture begins to refill at the chamber at a velocity V_{inj} .

The drawbacks of this quasi 1D model are: 1) a single stable detonation wave around the annulus, 2) interaction between the shocks and boundary layer as well as the deflagration to detonation are simplified, leading to an overestimation of pressure gain, and 3) there is no injection of fuel-air mixture in the expansion region.

A summary of the quasi 1D RDC model is shown in fig. 2. The modelling of quasi 1D RDC is divided into three parts: 1). Injection, 2). RDC, 3). Outlet. The summary shows the parameters used in this model as well as the source of the parameters.

1) In the injector model, the critical pressure and temperature are calculated using the isentropic relations. The injection Mach number is given as an initial guess which is used to calculate the injector pressure, temperature and velocity. 2) In the RDC section, the CJ conditions are determined using the shock-detonation toolbox. The experimental results of Sichel and Foster [17] is used for the calculation of detonation wave height and pressure decay after the detonation wave. Depending on the convergence of mass flow rate of reactants and products, the injector Mach number changes and M_{inj} is found using an iterative loop. 3) In the outlet section, the outlet total pressure is determined using the pressure distribution at inlet and the oblique shock flow parameters such as shock flow number and pressure ratio across oblique shock. The outlet total temperature is found using the enthalpy and entropy balance at the RDC exit. The velocity distribution at the outlet is determined using the relations from Endo [18] and with kinetic energy balance. Finally, the time period and frequency is calculated as a function of CJ velocity and circumference of RDC.

Fig. 2 Summary of the quasi 1D RDC model

A. Pre-detonation Parameters

The injector model used in the quasi 1D model is explained in this section. The pressure and temperature at the throat of the injector are referred to as the critical pressure and critical temperature as once the pressure reaches the critical pressure, the flow becomes choked. The parameters from plenum to injection are shown in fig. 1b. The critical pressure P_{cr} and the critical temperature T_{cr} can be obtained as function of the plenum parameters P_p and T_p and are shown in eqn. (1) and eqn. (2).

$$P_{cr} = P_p \left(\frac{2}{\gamma + 1} \right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1}} \quad (1)$$

$$T_{cr} = T_p \left(\frac{2}{\gamma + 1} \right) \quad (2)$$

Applying the conservation of mass and energy, the outlet flow parameters of the injectors as in fig. 1b can be determined using eqn. (3) - eqn. (5), where the parameter M_{inj} is an initial guess.

$$P_{inj} = \frac{A_{cr}}{A_{inj}} \frac{P_p}{M_{inj}} \left[\frac{\gamma + 1}{2 + (\gamma - 1)M_{inj}^2} \right]^{1/2} \left(\frac{2}{\gamma + 1} \right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1}} \quad (3)$$

$$T_{inj} = \left[\frac{2}{2 + (\gamma - 1)M_{inj}^2} \right] T_p \quad (4)$$

$$V_{inj} = M_{inj}(\gamma RT_{inj})^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

B. Post Detonation Parameters

The post detonation parameters such as the theoretical value of CJ velocity V_{CJ} , P_{CJ} , T_{CJ} and other CJ parameters are calculated using the Shock and Detonation tool box [19] as a function of the injection flow parameters. The peripheral velocity of the detonation front U_{CJ} as shown in fig. 1a can be calculated using the expression $U_{CJ} = V_{CJ} \cos(\beta)$.

C. Detonation front height

Several studies [12, 16, 20] have presented an empirical relation between the detonation height h_{det} and the experimental cell size λ as, $h_{det} = (12 \pm 5)\lambda$. Then, the detonation height can be calculated iteratively. In this study, a different approach has been chosen for the calculation of detonation wave height. If the detonation front is assumed to be straight, from fig. 3, we can derive eqn. (6), where β is a function of V_{CJ} and V_{inj} as shown in fig. 1a.

Fig. 3 Detonation front height calculation

$$\tan\beta = \frac{h_{det}}{\Delta\theta_{refilling}} \quad (6)$$

The eqn. (6) has two unknowns namely, h_{det} and $\Delta\theta_{refilling}$. Sichel and Foster [17] conducted experiments with a 4x4x20ft bag filled with fuel-air mixture and ignited from one end. Experimental values of pressure and impulse behind the detonation wave obtained using the pressure sensors. Experimental studies [17] have shown that $h_{det}/\Delta\theta_{expansion} = 2.90$. The experiments were carried out for various mixtures and for equivalence ratios from 0.6 to 1.6. As the circumference of the annulus C is known, the $\Delta\theta_{refilling} = C - 2.90h_{det}$. Therefore, the eqn. (6) becomes,

$$\tan\beta = \frac{h_{det}}{C - 2.90h_{det}} \quad (7)$$

From the eqn. (7), the detonation front height can be calculated and the refilling, expansion length can be determined. If the detonation front is not assumed to be straight, then \tan can be changed to \sin . As the angle β is small, the \tan and \sin values are almost the same which reduces the impact of this simplifying assumption.

D. Inlet Pressure and Temperature Distribution

From fig. 1a, the pressure attains its peak at θ_{det} and then decays to below the critical pressure where the fresh mixture begins to refill the chamber. The pressure distribution has three regions which are shown in eqn. (8). The function $f(\xi)$ is a function of a non-dimensional distance ξ , ($\xi = \theta r/h_{det}$) which is given by the experiment of Sichel and Foster [17]. The pressure decay model is shown in the appendix.

$$P(\theta) = \begin{cases} P_{cr}, & \theta = \theta_{inj} \\ P_{CJ}f(\xi), & \theta_{inj} < \theta \leq \theta_{det} \\ P_{inj}, & elsewhere \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Similarly, the temperature distribution can be calculated using eqn. (9).

$$T(\theta) = \begin{cases} T_{cr}, & \theta = \theta_{inj} \\ T_{CJ} \left[\frac{P(\theta)}{P_{CJ}} \right]^{\frac{R_{CJ}}{c_{pCJ}}}, & \theta_{inj} < \theta \leq \theta_{det} \\ T_{inj}, & elsewhere \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

E. Inlet Axial and Azimuthal Velocity Distribution

The reactants are considered to enter the combustor at a constant velocity of V_{inj} . Therefore, the axial velocity distribution is given by eqn. (10),

$$V_x(\theta) = \begin{cases} 0, & \theta_{inj} < \theta \leq \theta_{det} \\ V_{inj}, & elsewhere \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The azimuthal velocity distribution is given by eqn. (11). The $f(P, \rho, a)$ is calculated using the Taylor wave velocity.

$$V_\theta(\theta) = \begin{cases} a_{CJ}, & \theta = \theta_{det} \\ f(V_\theta, P, \rho, a), & \theta_{inj} < \theta < \theta_{det} \\ 0, & elsewhere \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

F. Convergence criteria

The convergence criterion is that the mass flow rate of the reactants should be the same as that of the products.

$$\dot{m}_{rea} = \frac{A_{cr}}{A_{inj}} \Delta\theta_{refilling} w_c P_p \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{RT_p}} \left(\frac{\gamma + 1}{2} \right)^{\frac{\gamma+1}{2(1-\gamma)}} \quad (12)$$

$$\dot{m}_{pdt} = \frac{P_{inj} w_c U_{CJ} h_{det}}{RT_{inj}} \quad (13)$$

G. Outlet Parameters

1. Outlet Total Pressure

Braun [21] suggested that it is sufficient to assume that the exit pressure is the mean of the pressure distribution for a reduced order model. Ji [16] determined the averaged outlet pressure using the mass flow averaged method. For the reduced order RDC models, the oblique shocks are neglected which results in increase in pressure gain. In this work, the oblique shock is taken into account. The outlet total pressure is calculated using the mass flow averaged of the pressure distribution at the inlet, shock flow number and pressure ratio across the oblique shock.

The mass flow average of pressure distribution at inlet is calculated by eqn. (14).

$$P_{t,detavg} = \frac{\int_0^{2\pi} \rho V r P(\theta) d\theta}{\int_0^{2\pi} \rho V r d\theta} \quad (14)$$

For the quasi 1D RDC model, the mass flow can be calculated only at the inlet and at the outlet and the mass flow is constant throughout the combustor. Thus, the eqn. (14) can be simplified to eqn. (15) as suggested by Ji [16].

$$P_{t,detavg} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} P(\theta) d\theta \quad (15)$$

From the fig. 1a, we can divide the pressure distribution to 1) before detonation wave, 2) in the expansion wave regime and 3) after the expansion regime. The eqn. (16) shows the pressure distribution at three regime in the inlet.

$$P_{t,detavg} = \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi x_1} \int_0^{\theta_{inj-1}} P_{inj} d\theta \right\} + \left\{ \frac{P_{CJ} h_{det}}{2\pi \Delta\theta_{expansion}} \int_0^{\xi} f(\xi) d\xi \right\} + \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi x_2} \int_{\theta_{det+1}}^{2\pi} P_{inj} d\theta \right\} \quad (16)$$

where $x_1 = \theta_{inj-1} - 0$ and $x_2 = 2\pi - \theta_{det+1}$

In this model, the oblique shock strength is assumed to be constant along the length of the combustor. The formulation of oblique shock is done using the shock flow number which is defined as the fraction of mass flow that goes through the oblique shock and the pressure ratio across the oblique shock. The oblique shock parameters are explained in section IV.B.

As mentioned before, the outlet total pressure is calculated using the average of the pressure distribution at the inlet, shock flow number and pressure ratio across the oblique shock which is shown in eqn. (17).

$$P_{t,out} = \begin{cases} P_{t,detavg}(1 - sfn) + P_{t,detavg}(sfn)(\pi_{ob}), & sfn < 1 \\ P_{t,detavg}(sfn)(\pi_{ob}) - P_{t,dob}(sfn - 1)(\pi_{ob}), & sfn > 1 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

The pressure gain is given by the eqn. (18).

$$P_{gain} = \frac{P_{t,out} - P_{t,in}}{P_{t,in}} \quad (18)$$

2. Outlet Total Temperature

The exit total temperature can be calculated iteratively using the total enthalpy and the entropy at the exit which are explained below.

$$h_{t,out} = c_{p,out}T_{t,out} = h_{t,in} + q \quad (19)$$

where, the heat release q can be given as,

$$q = \eta_c \Delta h_{f,pdt} n_{pdt} \quad (20)$$

The exit entropy can be calculated using eqn. (21). The entropy generation due to the detonation front is calculated using the Shock and Detonation tool box [19] and s_{ob} calculation is shown in section IV.B.

$$s_{out} = s_{in} + c_{p,out} \ln \left[\frac{T_{t,out}}{T_{t,in}} \right] - R_{out} \ln \left[\frac{P_{t,out}}{P_{t,in}} \right] = s_{CJ} + s_{ob} \quad (21)$$

The exit static pressure can be fixed and then the exit mach number, exit static temperature and exit velocity can be calculated using the isentropic relations.

H. Outlet Velocity Distribution

The azimuthal velocity distribution at the outlet can be calculated using the relationship given by Endo [18].

$$V_{\theta,out}(\theta) = V_{ex} - \frac{1}{1 + \gamma_{CJ}} \left[\frac{\theta}{\frac{C}{U_{CJ}} - t(\theta)} \right] \quad (22)$$

where $V_{ex} = \frac{U_{CJ}}{2(1 + \gamma_{CJ})}$.

The averaged axial velocity can be calculated using kinetic energy conservation as shown in eqn. (23).

$$\bar{V}_{x,out} = \sqrt{\bar{V}_{out}^2 - \bar{V}_{\theta,out}^2} \quad (23)$$

The axial velocity distribution at the outlet can be calculated using eqn. (24).

$$V_{x,out}(\theta) = \bar{V}_{x,out} - \frac{1}{1 + \gamma_{CJ}} \left[\frac{\theta}{\frac{C}{\bar{V}_{out,x}} - t(\theta)} \right] \quad (24)$$

I. Time Period and Frequency

According to the model, there is only one stable detonation wave rotating around the annulus. Thus the annulus wave time period is given as,

$$\tau = \frac{C}{n_{wave} U_{CJ}} \quad (25)$$

The frequency of the cycle can be calculated by,

$$f = \frac{1}{\tau} \quad (26)$$

J. Overview of Quasi 1D model

The flow chart of the the quasi 1D RDC model is shown in fig. 4. The given parameters to the quasi 1D RDC model includes the inlet plenum pressure, plenum temperature, geometry of RDC and fixed static pressure at outlet. The flow parameters in the injector plane is calculated using the critical pressure, critical temperature, throat-to-injector area ratio and initial guess for injection Mach number. With the first initial guess of the injection parameters, the CJ conditions are determined using the shock and detonation toolbox. The fixed ratio of $h_{det}/\Delta\theta_{expansion}$ from Sichel and Foster experiments [17], the detonation wave height is determined. Also, the pressure decay behind the detonation wave is also modelled using the experimental results of Sichel and Foster [17]. The mass flow rate convergence is checked and if the convergence is not satisfied, depending on the value of \dot{m}_{rea} and \dot{m}_{pdt} , the injection Mach number is changed and the loop restarts from injection flow parameters. Once, the convergence criteria is satisfied, the model moves to the calculation of RDC outlet flow parameters. The outlet total pressure is calculated as a function of pressure distribution at inlet, shock flow number and pressure ratio across oblique shock. The outlet total temperature is found in an iterative loop of enthalpy and entropy at exit. Then, with the fixed static pressure at the outlet, other exit flow parameters are calculated using isentropic relations. Finally, the axial and azimuthal velocity distribution is determined from Endo's model [18] and kinetic energy balance. The time period and frequency is found as a ratio of U_{CJ} and circumference of RDC.

Fig. 4 Overall Flow chart of the quasi 1D RDC model

III. 0D RDC model

As mentioned before, for a reduced order model, the outlet total pressure can be calculated from the mass flow average of the pressure distribution at the inlet [16]. As for a 0D model, geometrical parameters are not specified. The oblique shock must therefore be neglected as the detonation wave height and axial length cannot be determined. Thus, for a 0D model, the RDC is simplified as: Injection, Detonation wave, Outlet. The mass flow average of pressure distribution is given in eqn. (16). The integration of first and third term on the right side is P_{inj} as the reactants enters the combustor at a constant velocity in this model. The second term on the right side has two quantities which have length dimensions, namely, h_{det} and $\Delta\theta_{expansion}$. From [17], the value of the ratio is known to be 2.90. The integration limit for the second term will be from 0 to 2.90. Therefore, for the 0D approach, the outlet pressure can be rewritten from eqn. (16) to eqn. (27).

$$P_{t,out,0D} = P_{inj,0D} + \frac{P_{CJ}}{2\pi \cdot 2.90} \int_0^{2.90} f(\xi) d\xi + P_{inj,0D} \quad (27)$$

For the 0D model, the injection pressure can be formulated as in eqn. (28),

$$P_{inj,0D} = GP_p \left[\frac{\gamma + 1}{2 + (\gamma - 1)} \right]^{1/2} \left(\frac{2}{\gamma + 1} \right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1}} \quad (28)$$

where G is the correction factor which includes the effect of A_{cr}/A_{inj} and M_{inj} , so that the pressure gain is not over estimated. The value of G is user defined and can taken as less than 1.

The total temperature for the 0D model can be calculated using the exact approach of the quasi 1D model as shown from eqn. (19) - eqn. (21). The parameter T_{inj} can taken as the same as T_p as the effect of M_{inj} with respect to T_{inj} is negligible.

IV. Results and Discussion

Simulations were performed by the quasi 1D RDC for various RDC geometry, such as 1) for Schwer's, which was compared with 3D CFD and 2D MOC, and 2) for TU Berlin RDC, which was validated against experimental data and 3D LES for outlet parameters. The oblique shock is formulated using the shock flow number generated by the in-house 2D Euler solver. It was found that sfn and h_{det}/L form an exponential curve [22]. The axial and azimuthal velocity distributions for two inlet conditions are carried out and compared with 2D LES and 3D LES. Finally, the parametric analysis is done for varying plenum temperature and equivalence ratio, and the P_{gain} is plotted.

A. Model Validation

The quasi 1D RDC model is compared with 3D CFD model [10]. The input parameter for Schwer's CFD validation of RDC is given Tab. 1.

Table 1 Input parameter for RDC validation case with Schwer CFD [10]

Parameters	Value
Fuel-Oxidizer	Hydrogen-Air
Equivalence ratio	1
Circumference of the combustor (mm)	439.8
Width of the combustor (mm)	10
A_{cr} / A_{inj}	0.2
Plenum pressure (bar)	10
Plenum temperature (K)	300

Fig. 5 Comparison of pressure and temperature distribution on the thrust wall between the Quasi 1D model and 3D CFD solution

From fig. 5, we were able to see a reasonably good agreement between the current model and the 3D CFD model.

Fig. 6 Comparison of mass flow rate with 3D CFD and h_{det} with Method of Characteristic (MOC) [12]

Figure. 6a shows the comparison of the mass flow rate of the reactants \dot{m}_{rea} for different plenum pressure between the 3D CFD model [10] and the current model. Figure. 6b also shows the comparison of the height of detonation front h_{det} for different radius of the combustor between the 2D MOC model [12] and the current model. We can see that the detonation front height increases with increasing radius of the combustor in both the models. The comparison of \dot{m}_{rea} and h_{det} shows a reasonable agreement with an average difference of 9% and 5%.

The TU Berlin RDC is simulated by the quasi 1D RDC model and compared with the experimental and 3D LES results. The configuration of the TUB RDC is given in Tab. 2.

Table 2 Input parameter for RDC validation with Experimental and 3D LES non-premixed [23]

Parameters	Value
Fuel-Oxidizer	Hydrogen-Air
Equivalence ratio	1
Circumference of the combustor (mm)	260
Axial length of the combustor (mm)	112
Width of the combustor (mm)	7
Plenum pressure (bar)	7.42
Plenum temperature (K)	291

Table 3 Comparison between Experimental, 3D LES [23] and Quasi 1D.

Parameters	Experimental non-premixed	3D LES non-premixed	Quasi 1D premixed
Wave type	Single	Single	Single
Inlet total pressure (bar)	7.42	7.42	7.42
Inlet total temperature (K)	291	291	291
Outlet total pressure (bar)	3.12	3.17	3.977
Pressure gain	-0.58	-0.57	-0.464
Outlet total temperature (K)	-	2142.78	2189.20
Mass flow rate (kg/s)	-	0.445	0.462
Wave frequency (Hz)	6287	7509	7563

From Tab. 3, we could see the comparison of quasi 1D model with experimental and 3D LES. The pressure gain is slightly overestimated by the 1D model. This difference could be due to the simplified injector, oblique shock

formulation and also due to the down-scaling of three dimensional to quasi 1D. The outlet total temperature and the mass flow rate shows great agreement with 3D LES. The frequency is higher for the quasi 1D model as it assumes a stable CJ detonation wave rotating around the annulus.

Fig. 7 Temperature contour and pressure distribution comparison between the quasi 1D model and 3D LES [23]

In order to determine the pressure profile in the 3D LES non-premixed case, where the air is injected perpendicular to the combustor and there is a significant amount of non-ideal mixing near the floor of the combustor, we decided that the best axial location for comparison with the 1D case would be to consider an axial location located slightly above the floor but within the detonation region. Thus, all the distribution between the quasi 1D and 3D LES are compared at $x = 10\text{mm}$ from inlet as denoted by the black line in fig. 7a.

The 3D LES has been simulated by monitoring pressure at various span in the radial direction at $z = 3\%$, 25% , 50% , 75% and 97% , where $z = 3\%$ is near the inner wall and $z = 97\%$ is near the outer wall near air injector. Figure. 7b shows the pressure distribution comparison between the quasi 1D model and 3D LES at $z = 50\%$ and $z = 75\%$, and the mean of all radial spans. We can see from the figure that the quasi 1D model is somewhat comparable with 3D LES for the mean and $z = 50\%$. For $z = 75\%$, the peak pressure does not match well. This shows that the quasi 1D model is able to capture the flow characteristics at mean and mid span but not in a three dimensional space.

B. Oblique Shock

The oblique shock formulation is intended to account for the losses in this region. The shock flow number is defined as the fraction of mass flow that goes through the oblique shock. That is, for a shock flow number 0.5, 50% of mass flow passes through the oblique shock and for shock flow number 1.2, all of the mass passes the shock once and 20% passes a second time. In the fig. 8, the white line represents the shock flow number. With the in-house 2D Euler model [22], the shock flow number is found to be well approximated as a function of the ratio of detonation height to the axial length of combustor. From the quasi 1D model, the detonation wave height is calculated and the axial length of the combustor is a given parameter. As seen in fig. 9a, the sfn and h_{det}/L form an exponential curve, with a correlation of $sfn = 2.89e^{-6.41 \frac{h_{det}}{L}}$. Also, the averaged entropy generated by the oblique shock with respect to sfn is given in fig. 9b.

Fig. 8 Stream lines passing through oblique shocks are shown in white and stream line not passing through oblique shocks are shown in black (from [22])

Fig. 9 Oblique shock parameters

The analytical entropy generation is used for the calculation of total pressure ratio across oblique shock and the analytical entropy can be calculated from the averaged entropy generation as shown in eqn. (29).

$$s_{ob,an} = \begin{cases} \frac{s_{ob,avg}}{sfn}, & sfn < 1 \\ s_{ob,avg}(sfn), & sfn > 1 \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

As the total temperature is constant across the oblique shock, the pressure ratio can be calculated as in eqn. (30),

$$\pi_{ob} = \frac{P_{t,dob}}{P_{t,uob}} = -exp\left(\frac{s_{ob,an}}{R_{CJ}}\right) \quad (30)$$

where $P_{t,uob} = P_{CJ}$

Fig. 10 Calculation of oblique shock in quasi 1D model

The flow chart for how the outlet total pressure is determined using the shock flow number is given in fig. 10. With π_{ob} calculated, the total pressure at the outlet can be determined by eqn. (17). The pressure gain with different values of h_{det}/L is then plotted in fig. 11. We can see that the pressure gain increases with increases in h_{det}/L , which is due to decrease in sfn with increase in h_{det}/L and reduction in π_{ob} .

Fig. 11 Pressure gain as function of h_{det}/L

C. Velocity Distribution

The inlet and outlet distribution of the axial and azimuthal flow parameters are discussed in this section. The geometry used for these results are same as in Tab. 3.

(a) Azimuthal velocity distribution between 2D LES and quasi 1D model

(b) Azimuthal velocity distribution between 3D LES and quasi 1D model

Fig. 12 Azimuthal velocity distribution at inlet

(a) Azimuthal velocity distribution between 2D LES and quasi 1D model

(b) Azimuthal velocity distribution between 3D LES and quasi 1D model

Fig. 13 Azimuthal velocity distribution at outlet

The calculation of inlet azimuthal velocity is given in eqn. 11. The azimuthal velocity is zero in the refilling region while in the expansion region, due to the presence of the detonation wave, the azimuthal velocity is non-zero. The quasi 1D RDC model uses the Taylor wave expansion which is a function of azimuthal velocity, pressure, gas constant and speed of sound in the expansion region. Between the 2D LES and quasi 1D fig. 12a the azimuthal velocity shows a good agreement, while for the 3D LES, the azimuthal velocity is negative in the refilling zone. This is due to the fact that, for 3D LES the distribution is shown at $x = 10mm$ as shown in fig. 7a. As we go from the inlet to the outlet of the combustor, the azimuthal velocity tends to be negative at certain region, thus we could see the negative value for V_θ for 3D LES in fig. 12b. The outlet azimuthal velocity is modelled similar to [18, 21] with few modifications as their model predicts the outlet distribution of PDC, this eqn. 22 is for the RDC case. The outlet distribution of quasi 1D model follows similar trend with the 3D LES model. For the quasi 1D model, the velocity distribution is approximately linear, while for 2D and 3D LES it is less so. While not exact, this simple model provides decent enough fidelity for the azimuthal velocity distribution at the outlet in terms of the magnitude and approximate rate of variation.

(a) Axial velocity distribution between 2D LES and quasi 1D model

(b) Axial velocity distribution between 3D LES and quasi 1D model

Fig. 14 Axial velocity distribution at inlet

(a) Axial velocity distribution between 2D LES and quasi 1D model

(b) Axial velocity distribution between 3D LES and quasi 1D model

Fig. 15 Axial velocity distribution at outlet

For the quasi 1D model, the inlet axial velocity distribution is calculated using eqn. 10. As previously stated, the reactant mixture is injected at a constant velocity V_{inj} and is zero in expansion region behind the detonation. However for the 2D LES, the inlet axial velocity increases just before the detonation wave ($\theta = 190$), decreases to zero after the wave ($\theta = 170$) and increases gradually. The 3D LES V_x is higher because the chosen axial location is at $x = 10mm$ as mentioned in fig. 7a. The inlet axial velocity distribution as shown in fig. 14 is not particularly well matched with 2D LES and 3D LES. The primary motive of the quasi 1D model, however, is to predict the outlet parameters such as pressure gain, T_{out} , axial and azimuthal velocity distribution. Thus, the inlet distribution is not major focus initially, and is a potential area of future work. The distribution of velocity in both components as shown in fig. 15 however exhibits and reasonably good match for such a low order model.

D. Parametric Analysis

A parametric study was conducted with the current model in order to check if the model follows the trends of the physical RDC. The inlet parameters such as plenum temperature and equivalence ratio are varied and the pressure gain for the variation have been plotted. The comparison has been done against the in-house 2D Euler solver [22].

(a) Pressure gain as a function of Plenum temperature

(b) Detonation parameters as a function of Plenum temperature

Fig. 16 Influence of Plenum Temperature to Pressure gain.

(a) Pressure gain as a function of Equivalence ratio

(b) Detonation parameters as a function of Equivalence ratio

Fig. 17 Influence of Equivalence ratio to pressure gain.

Figure. 16 shows the influence of plenum temperature on the pressure gain. We can see that, the higher the plenum temperature, the lower the pressure gain. This is due to the fact that, for higher inlet temperature, the intensity of the detonation wave, that is, the strength of the detonation wave is reduced, and so does the pressure gain. The increase in plenum temperature leads to the reduction in P_{CJ} and the detonation wave Mach number M_{CJ} , thus reducing the peripheral velocity of the detonation wave.

From the fig. 17 the relationship between the equivalence ratio and the pressure gain can be seen. The pressure gain increases slightly with increasing in equivalence ratio. For higher equivalence ratios, the strength of the detonation wave is higher, which increases the pressure gain. Here, P_{CJ} and M_{CJ} increases when the equivalence ratio is increased.

From the fig. 16 and fig. 17, we can conclude that the pressure gain is slightly positively correlated with equivalence ratio and negatively correlated with plenum temperature.

V. Conclusion

The paper presented a simple yet accurate quasi 1D model for Rotating Detonation Combustors and is validated against experimental and various CFD models. Firstly, the injection parameters were modelled using the conservation of mass and energy equations. The detonation parameters were calculated using the SD Toolbox. In this work, the detonation wave height is calculated using the ratio of $h_{det}/\Delta\theta_{refilling}$ and from Sichel and Foster experiments. The pressure decay was also modelled from their experiments. The oblique shock was formulated using the shock flow number and entropy generated by the oblique shock. The outlet total pressure equation was obtained as a function of mass flow average of pressure distribution at the inlet, the shock flow number, and the pressure ratio across the oblique shock. The outlet temperature was calculated with the entropy and enthalpy balance between inlet and outlet. The outlet distribution of axial and azimuthal velocity were modelled.

The pressure and temperature distributions, mass flow rate and detonation wave height of quasi 1D model were

validated against 3D CFD model and 2D MOC model. The pressure gain, outlet temperature, mass flow rate and frequency were compared with experimental, 3D LES and tabulated in Tab. 3. The pressure gain was overestimated by the quasi 1D model. This could be due to the simplified injection model and down-scaling of 3D to 1D. The pressure distribution of the quasi 1D model was compared with various radial spans from the 3D LES results. The comparison showed that the model was able to predict the mean and mid span better than at other locations. A parametric analysis of pressure gain as a function of plenum temperature and equivalence ratio were plotted with the in-house 2D Euler solver. The results showed that the pressure gain positively correlates with equivalence ratio and negatively correlates with plenum temperature. Finally, the azimuthal and axial velocity distribution at the inlet and outlet were compared with the 2D and 3D LES. The inlet axial velocity distribution didn't show a good match with LES results while the other distribution showed a fine agreement with one another. The major motive of the model is to forecast RDC outlet flow parameters that can be utilized for lower order cycle analysis, which the model was able to do.

In this paper, the injection process was simplified, the combustion efficiency was taken as a constant value and no outlet restriction was considered which could have the effect of back pressure. Inclusion of these characteristics would be recommended for future work.

Appendix

The function $f(\xi)$ can be taken from the graph of Sichel and Foster [17] experimental values of the pressure decay behind the detonation front. Figure 18 shows the pressure decay as a function of P_{CJ} and ξ where ξ varies from 0 to 2.90. The function $f(\xi)$ can be calculated using a fifth order polynomial function from fig. 18, which is given in eqn. 31.

$$f(\xi) = 0.0282\xi^5 - 0.2604\xi^4 + 0.8681\xi^3 - 1.1357\xi^2 + 0.0623\xi + 0.9988 = \frac{P(\theta)}{P_{CJ}} \quad (31)$$

where $\xi = \frac{\theta_{det} - \theta}{h_{det}}$ and θ are the points in the expansion zone.

Fig. 18 Pressure decay behind the detonation front [17]

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